

ISSUES OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION IN THE GLOBAL MEDIA LANDSCAPE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the objects of intellectual property in Internet publications, describes the ways in which protection arises and analyzes the violations that occur in world and local practice.

Intellectual property is an integral part of the media. Every newspaper, online publication or TV channel uses a lot of intellectual property. Let's define the main forms of content that are placed in the media:

- Text content: news, articles, reviews, interviews, blogs, reports.
- Graphic content: photographs, illustrations, pictures, diagrams, infographics.
- Audio content : music, sound effects, podcasts, radio broadcasts.
- Video content: videos, news stories, reports, documentaries, commercials, online broadcasts.
- Interactive content: applications, online games, voting, polls, forums, chats ¹.

Copyright for works in Internet publications extends to articles, photographs, reports, video and audio materials. It is important to note that copyright arises and is assigned to the author automatically at the time of creation of the work and does not require registration. The author has the exclusive right to use the work and control its distribution. Usually, the right to own and transfer the rights of the editorial office is reflected in the employment contract when hiring for an online publication.

Copyright in the text within the framework of labor and creative activity in the media means that the author of the text has the exclusive right to use the content of the material and control its distribution ². This right includes the right to copy, distribute, publish, create derivative works and make other uses of the text. This aspect is also regulated by the labor agreement between the parties and applies to any genre presented on the publication's website - news and analytical articles, interviews and comments, reviews and reports. Copyright in the text arises at the time of its writing.

¹Правовое регулирование медиа: Учебное пособие для вузов / В.В. Макашова. – М.: Издательство «Аспект Пресс», 2022. – 220 с.

²Law "On Copyright and Related Rights" // <https://lex.uz/docs/1023494> [date of access: 05/17/2023]

Today, the practice of applying legal methods to improve the media business from different angles is common. Employees, knowing that their creative and intellectual work is protected, are highly motivated to work and improve as specialists, and this, in turn, has a positive impact on the media landscape and the final media product .

Media professionals are systematically confronted with intellectual property disputes. Intellectual property infringements in the media can have a range of consequences, from minor ones that only affect the motivation of employees, to significant and destructive ones, for example, damage to the image of the publication. Consider the main violations that occur in the online media space:

- Text copyright infringement;
- Piracy;
- Lack of attribution of authorship;
- Violation of related rights;
- Illegal copying;
- Plagiarism;
- Copyright infringement on photos and videos;
- Unfair use of a trademark;
- Patent infringement;
- Misquoting³.

The most commonly used type of content in Internet publications is text, which can be placed in different genre boxes, which also determine whether the content is protected by copyright. It is known that copyright in a text arises automatically at the time of creation of a unique work. But in order for copyright to be considered to have arisen, the following conditions must be met:

- Creative component: the text should be the result of a person's creative activity, have originality, demonstrate intellectual work and have elements of novelty.
- Expressiveness: The text must be expressed in a specific form, such as a handwritten note or an electronic document. That is, the spoken text aloud cannot be defined as an object of copyright.
- Protectable : The text must fall under the legal category of a work that is subject to copyright protection. It can be fiction, scientific articles, journalism, poetry, computer programs and other forms of literary works.

If the text meets the above criteria, then copyright will arise automatically - additional registration is optional.

Photos are also an integral part of online publications. Copyright in a photo arises automatically when an original photographic work is created. In order for copyright to be considered to have arisen, the following conditions must also be met: originality, creativity, protectability , and expressiveness. The photo should reflect the unique creative approach of the author, which is manifested in the composition, lighting, angle.

But not all objects of intellectual property are protected at the moment of creation. For example, trademark protection is not regulated by the institution of copyright. A distinctive

³Richter A. G., Legal framework for regulating the activities of Internet media, 2013

sign is a graphic designation for identifying goods or services of a certain organization. Trademarks are protected through their registration with the relevant intellectual property authorities.

Having dealt with the main objects and how protection arises, we will certainly proceed to the analysis of violations that occur in world and local practice.

Plagiarism is the presentation of other people's ideas, thoughts or text materials as one's own. It can occur in different areas, including the media. In the context of Internet publications, plagiarism manifests itself in the copying of texts, photos, videos and other types of content without proper permission or attribution of the source. This serious violation has legal consequences for the ill-wisher. As for the impact on the editorial office - from lowering the motivation of an employee to damaging the reputation of the editorial office. And the second outcome is possible in the case when the online publication itself violates copyright. For example, the authors of the site take author's articles from the Internet for rewriting and, performing their work poorly, as a result, they get a seemingly new text, but with very low uniqueness. Here, an important aspect is the control on the part of the editors and the ethics of the authors themselves. The topic of plagiarism is indeed a matter of journalistic ethics and the integrity of the editorial staff.

Misquoting also leads to copyright infringement, as well as a decrease in reader confidence. It may include the use of other people's words and thoughts without indicating the source, incorrect quotation, or the use of a large amount of material without the consent of the author. Such a violation can occur both by accident due to the low competence of the author and editor, and also deliberately in order to conceal the fact of using someone else's material. Another way is to rephrase the original quote, which may be due to the unprofessionalism of the journalist or to change the key meaning. The citation rules also deal with ethical issues and include the obligatory attribution of the author. The text of the original quotation should also be reproduced exactly.

Consider another related concept - the attribution of authorship. In the context of copyright, it refers to the indication of the name or other information about the author of a work when it is used or made public ⁴. Attribution allows you to attribute a work to a specific author and publicly acknowledge his rights to this work. This aspect is not mandatory and is usually regulated by an employment agreement between the author and the editors, it is also more about ethics and respect for the rights of the creator. As a rule, attribution includes:

- Name or pseudonym of the author;
- The date the object was created;
- Other information that identifies the author.

Violation of attribution of authorship can lead to distortion of information and mislead the reader. Another important aspect is that it is thanks to the indication of authorship that the copyright holder can count on a fee or other remuneration.

Online publications face copyright infringement on photos, and also act as infringers themselves ⁵. This can happen when using a photo in articles without the consent of the

⁴Great Soviet Encyclopedia Attribution // <https://goo.su/cJa0h> [date of access: 05/10/2023]

⁵Article by Doctor of Philology I.A. Pankeeva "Copyright of a photojournalist"

copyright holder or when changing the photo also without his permission. Another type of violation is the use of photos for commercial purposes without the consent of the author. Video copyright infringement in the media is expressed in the use of videos without the permission of the author, the modification or editing of videos without the consent of the copyright holder, and the publication of videos that are the intellectual property of other people. In this case, the copyright holder has the right to demand the removal of the video in violation of his rights or to demand the termination of further use of his intellectual property.

There are objects of related rights in the media, such as interviews, videos, podcasts, articles with two or more authors ⁶. The illegal use of such works is also a violation, as well as the case when one of the authors of the works violates the agreement on related rights. The following are other examples of violations of related rights ⁷:

- the use of a melody as a background in a video without the permission of the copyright holder of the musical composition;
- using unique sound recording software infringing the copyrights of record companies;
- transmission of live broadcasts, such as sports matches, concerts and other events without the permission of the copyright holders;
- using frames from films, TV shows or other works as illustrations without the permission of the copyright holder.
- use of photographs and images for commercial purposes without the consent of the copyright owner.
- copying text from articles or books, violating the copyrights of a group of authors.

Many infringements of intellectual property in Internet publications and by the editors themselves can lead to financial losses and damage to the reputation of copyright holders, and can also undermine the trust of readers. That is why all participants in the media process need to be thoroughly aware of the objects that are protected in one way or another, as well as be aware of the possible consequences. More than once in this work it will be emphasized that not only a person from the outside can be a violator, but also the editorial staff themselves. Often, attackers pursue several goals - profiting from the consequences of the violation or personal motives.

Whatever the ideas of the violator, the task of media management and editors is to ensure the protection of intellectual property and such working conditions so that employees are not motivated to resort to illegal actions. Compliance with intellectual property laws and the use of modern protection technologies can help reduce the risk of infringement and ensure fair conditions for the use of content in the media.

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⁶Richter A. G., Legal framework for regulating the activities of Internet media, 2013

⁷Dissertation of the candidate of philological sciences N. A. Sheludyakova "Internet media in the aspect of copyright"

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